

**DEVELOPMENT OF CONSULTING SERVICES IN THE REPUBLIC
OF UZBEKISTAN IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY**

Kholbutaeva Shakhnoza Abduvalievna

Tashkent State Transport University,

Senior Lecturer of the Department of Transport Economics

E-mail: abdurazakova_shakhnoza@mail.ru

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Annotation

This article discusses the changes taking place in the world and in the economy of our country in the digital economy, as well as the role of consulting services in this area. The impact of digitalization of business activities in Uzbekistan, including consulting services, on the formation of a new structure of the economy will be considered.

Keywords: consulting, digital economy, business environment, entrepreneurship.

The interest in the digitalization of production and services, in turn, is leading to significant changes in the world economy and the rapid growth of this area. Digitalization of the economy helps businesses and individuals reduce costs by minimizing personal contact with customers, partners and government agencies that are actively involved in modern technologies and platforms. It also allows for faster and easier interactions, resulting in increased demand for network-based, digital or electronic economies.

The development of the digital economy in the Republic of Uzbekistan is also taking place in conjunction with standard economic criteria such as the coverage of information technology and the availability of infrastructure, the business environment, human capital and successful management tools. Consequently, economic development relies on them, which means that these criteria continue to play an important role in the development of the digital economy.

In the digital economy, the range of consulting services provided by consulting companies is expanding, and the activities of consulting organizations are focused on medium and large businesses. This is, of course, primarily due to the growth of competition and demand in the field of consulting services. In this regard, as the head of our state Sh.M.Mirziyoev said: "... now we need to take measures to improve the activities of the consulting service, ie consulting and legal assistance to businesses."

At present, there is a need in the country for management consulting services not only for small and medium-sized businesses, but also for improving the

country's governance. In particular, in order to eliminate problems in the field of governance, on September 8, 2017, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Decree No. PF-5185 "On approval of the Concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan" states: , requires the creation of an effective and high-quality operating system, the organization of harmonious activities of public administration and local executive authorities.

In the near future, the number of consulting companies in some regions is expected to exceed the city of Tashkent in some areas. This can be explained by the growing demand for various consulting services in the rest of the country. In particular, the attention paid to investment and innovation in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Kashkadarya, Syrdarya and Namangan regions creates the demand for this type of consulting services. It should be noted that in recent years in Tashkent and Samarkand, as a result of competition from consulting companies, a number of large consulting companies are squeezing out small ones. More than 70% of all consulting companies are located in Tashkent. It is followed by Samarkand (5%) and Namangan (4%).

In addition to the constant needs of customers in the automation of business processes, today the integration of management, production, work processes, digitization of collected data is one of the highest requirements. In this regard, the largest share of total revenues in the Russian consulting market in 2020 fell to IT consulting services, which accounted for 57% of total revenues or 40.63 billion rubles. rubles. The second-largest revenue in the year under review fell to financial consulting services, which accounted for 18 percent or \$ 12.57 billion. rubles. A total of 4.7 billion soums was provided to the participants of the legal services and tax consulting rating. rubles or 6.6%, HR-consulting - 2.43% of total revenues, consulting services in the field of strategic planning and marketing - 2.07 bln. rubles (2.9 percent). In 2020, 4.47 mln. rubles in the segment of consulting services in the manufacturing sector.

Demand for various areas of consulting services is also high among neighboring CIS countries. In particular, in early 2008, more than 4,700 consulting companies were registered in neighboring Kazakhstan, most of which provide consulting services related to the economic development of the regions. These consulting firms are located in Almaty, Atyrau and Astana. The most popular areas of consulting services are: financial, legal, strategic consulting, evaluation, marketing consulting, HR (personnel management) consulting, IT-consulting, industrial consulting. The main consumers of consulting services are

government agencies and national companies (development of feasibility studies, project estimates for public procurement).

The market of consulting services in Kazakhstan needs local and mainly consultants of large international or Russian consulting firms, which in turn requires the establishment of representative offices and branches of international firms.

Considering the above analysis, it can be said that consulting in the world economy has a separate conceptual basis to date. At the same time, the market of consulting services in the digital economy of our country is developing in line with the development of the economy.

References:

1. Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis - Tashkent. // People's speech, December 29, 2018.
2. <http://www.lex.uz/ru/docs/3331174>
3. goldenpages.uz